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Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
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- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
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- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
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- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari

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MECHANISMS AND BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the specific features of the business environment in the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the direct and indirect relationship between the direction of small business and private entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan and the business environment, and proposes scientific foundations aimed at developing and increasing the efficiency of small business entities.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, national economy, small business, private entrepreneurship, business environment.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekiston Respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda biznes muhitining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari, shuningdek, kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik yo‘nalishining biznes muhiti bilan bevosita va bilvosita bog‘liqligi tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, kichik biznes subyektlarini rivojlantirish va samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan ilmiy asoslar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: tadbirkorlik, milliy iqtisodiyot, kichik biznes, xususiy tadbirkorlik, biznes muhiti.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются специфические особенности бизнес-среды в развитии малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства в Республике Узбекистан, а также прямые и косвенные взаимосвязи между направлением малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства в Узбекистане и бизнес-средой. В работе предлагаются научные основы, направленные на развитие и повышение эффективности субъектов малого бизнеса.

Ключевые слова: предпринимательство, национальная экономика, малый бизнес, частное предпринимательство, бизнес-среда.

INTRODUCTION

The large-scale reforms carried out in New Uzbekistan in recent years are directly aimed at improving the population’s standard of living and enhancing the country’s socio-economic position

both in the region and globally. Naturally, one of the most effective tools for ensuring the success of these reforms is small business and private entrepreneurship. While large business entities are economically strong, they often struggle to adapt to external conditions, particularly during crises. In contrast, small business entities are more flexible and capable of responding to challenging circumstances. Therefore, it is crucial to develop a mechanism for fostering small business and private entrepreneurship in the country, along with strategies to improve the overall business environment.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

The development of small business and private entrepreneurship, along with the theoretical and methodological foundations of ensuring their sustainability and improving management mechanisms, has been widely covered in the works of foreign economic scholars such as M. William, Michael E. Porter, Joseph Schumpeter, Israel Kirzner, Douglas North, William Baumol, L. Mises, F. Hayek, E. Hargadon, McClelland, and others. Scientific research on the essence, theoretical foundations, and regional characteristics of small business and private entrepreneurship has also been conducted by CIS scholars, including L.I. Abalkin, D.V. Khodos, G.S. Seyalova, V.V. Radaev, V.M. Vlasova, A.M. Samozkin, V.G. Gutman, I.A. Rodionova, V.G. Medinsky, L.G. Sharshukova, and A.V. Busigin.

Joseph Schumpeter, in particular, developed the Innovation Theory, viewing small business development as a key factor in economic growth. He described small businesses as an “engine of innovation” and emphasized their ability to drive economic change through the introduction of new products, production methods, and processes.

The first studies on entrepreneurial activity date back to the 18th century, appearing in the works of R. Cantillon, A. Turgot, F. Quesnay, A. Smith, and J.B. Say. However, the concept of “entrepreneurship” in public discourse remains ambiguous to this day.

Theoretical aspects of small business and private entrepreneurship development in our country, as well as the challenges of crisis management, have been explored by Uzbek economic scholars such as M. Sharifkho'jaev, S.S. Gulyamov, Yo. Abdullaev, B.Yu. Khodiev, M.S. Kasymova, Q.M. Usmonov, and others. Small businesses and private entrepreneurship provide a fast and cost-effective solution for economic recovery, overcoming instability, and efficiently filling resource consumption markets. Small businesses, due to their flexibility, can quickly adapt to changes in consumer demand, playing a crucial role in maintaining equilibrium in the consumer market.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article analyzes the scientific works of domestic and foreign researchers, scientific literature, periodicals and uses systematic approach, economic analysis and comparison and descriptive methods in order to study theoretical and practical approaches to effective use of the experience of foreign advanced countries.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Small business and private entrepreneurship, as a sphere of rapid adaptation to changes of the economy, play an important role in saturating the domestic market with consumer goods, expanding new and modern types of services, and developing export potential. Due to the widespread implementation in practice of the decisions made to support small business and private entrepreneurship, the reduction of inspection work, the reduction of financial and time costs for doing business, the introduction of an electronic registration system, the number of registered and operating small business entities is rapidly increasing, and positive trends are also taking place in their economic indicators. The establishment of Chamber of Commerce and Industry in accordance with the Presidential Decree of July 7, 2004 is one of the strategic actions aimed at the broad development of entrepreneurship (figure 1).

Figure 1. Number of employed Americans in the United States by years (millions).

The main goal of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry is to create favorable conditions for the further development of private entrepreneurship and improve the business environment. According to the U.S. Small Business Association, small businesses with 500 or fewer employees account for 99.9% of all businesses in the U.S. and 99.7% of firms with salaried employees. Small businesses accounted for 162% of the new jobs created between 1995 and 2020, or 12.7 million, compared to 7.9 million of large businesses. A 2019 SBA report showed, Small businesses account for 44% of U.S. economic activity, in addition to the fact that its share of total employment in the U.S. is considered very high (Figure 1).

As you know, the economic sectors we aim to develop must receive state support. According to international experience, the primary government body responsible for supporting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in China is the Center for Business Coordination and Cooperation. This organization facilitates the creation of essential infrastructure for technological collaboration between national and foreign organizations in the field of business support. Its responsibilities include:

- small business problem studies and policy development
- creation of a comprehensive business development services system;

Assistance in the organization of trade exhibitions, fairs, business negotiations, training and consulting services.

Along with the Institute, the State Fund for the Development of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises is involved in the support of small and medium-sized businesses. Its main task is to protect legitimate income from aggression by all kinds of individuals and organizations, to protect the rights of small and medium-sized businesses in all areas (preferential loans, taxes, etc.) (figure 2).

Figure 2. Profile of the participants in the total employment of the small businesses².

1 <https://advocacy.sba.gov/2019/01/30/small-businesses-generate-44-percent-of-u-s-economic-activity/>
 2 <https://www.stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/small-business-and-entrepreneurship-2#:~:text=Kichik%20adbirkorlik%20subyektlarining%20jami%20bandlikdagi%20ulushi>

China, among many countries, has created and is improving public funds to stimulate the development of small and medium-sized enterprises. The main objective of these funds is to assist SMEs in obtaining bank loans to expand production. Along with government agencies, provincial administrations of China also provide support to the export development of SMEs at the expense of their budgets³

Small businesses and SMEs make up the majority of enterprises worldwide, and are important contributors to job creation and global economic development. They represent nearly 90% of businesses and over 50% of employment worldwide. In Uzbekistan in particular, this indicator is considered to be quite high, and the proof of this can be seen above (Table 1).

In general, the entrepreneurial environment is largely the result of the interdependence of the following four factors: legal, political, social and economic factors [3]. Business activity is dynamically developed through stimulus or recovery conditions, and in this case, the existing economic and legal environment in the country or country is favorable conditions for entrepreneurship. Since the role of small business and private entrepreneurship is a factor that keeps the country's economy stable, then it is natural to wonder why the business environment in our country is not organized at the level of China, the USA or other industrialized countries. As an answer to such a question, it can be said that one of the main factors is the fact that the activity of economic and social enterprises that should form the business environment is not fully in accordance with the requirements of the market economy [5]. An entrepreneurial city with a sufficiently developed business environment believes that there are five factors: resource base, entrepreneurial culture, motivational philosophy, strategy orientation, and management structure, so strengthening each of them will lead to the development of entrepreneurship in the city. An entrepreneurial city is essentially a new city policy in which different resources and coalitions try to increase the economic value of the city while maximizing investment attraction along with sustainability. In the literature, this policy is known as a tactical response to financial resource constraints and foreign policy pressures⁴.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The current state of innovation environment in the country does not allow to achieve a high level of development of innovation activity of small business in a short time. [2] Its development requires the formulation of specific measures and measures by the state. In this regard, the main emphasis should be primarily on the following:

- use of scientific and technical information by small businesses, reduction of high transaction costs for the implementation of innovative projects;
- testing new technologies for small enterprises and eliminating high risks in attracting them;
- stimulation of the creation of a market of financial and investment institutions that offer their resources for innovative developments and integration;
- increasing the interest of large enterprises from shared financing of innovative projects of small business entities as a contributing organization;
- Increasing the efficiency of the integration of science, education and production and developing the network of innovative intermediaries that interconnect them.

While the above suggestions are factors that influence the development of the business environment at the highest level, in some regions these factors may affect at different levels

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